

An Economic of the Nutritional Profile of Children in Meelaneelitha Nallur Block in Tirunelveli District

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Abstract

Food is the prime necessity of life. Food we eat is digested and assimilated in the body and used for its maintenance and growth. Food also provides energy for doing work. Man has exhibited much thought and foresight in cultivating a variety of grains, fruits, vegetables, nuts and oilseeds and in rearing birds and animals for use as food. Malnutrition is another serious health concern that India is found among all segments of the population, poor nutrition among women in childhood continues throughout their lives without full physical development. According to the NFHS-3 Survey, mother's education plays a significant role in deciding the level of malnutrition among her children women. Malnutrition among women is further exacerbated or compounded by heavy work demands, nutritional needs, eventually culminating into increased susceptibility to illness and consequent higher mortality (Khan: 2011). And hence, this research work is aimed to estimate the effects of malnutrition in early childhood, to identify the health problem of children in Meelaneelithanallur block due to malnutrition. Using both secondary and primary data from a sample 200 children in health sector – Nurses, Anganwadi teachers, women in primary health centre, midwife.

Keywords: Nutrition, Malnutrition, Physical stature, Economic factor.

Introduction

"Health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity"- WHO in 2007.

"Nutrition is the science of foods and its relationship to health. It includes all the processes involved in the taking in and utilization of food substances by which body as a whole or in any of its parts are accomplished. These processes are ingestion, digestion, absorption and utilization"-Dr. Shrinandan Bansal.

Health economics is the study of how scarce resources are allocated among alternative uses for the care of sickness and the promotion, maintenance and improvement of health, including the study of how health care and health related services, their cost and benefits, and health itself are distributed among in among individuals and groups in society.

The selection of foods best suited for promoting good health has been found out by trial and error by continued use. Use of milk of different mammals as foods for infants has been practiced from very early times. A considerable amount of information is now available on the nutritive value of foods and nutritional requirements. The present

knowledge of nutrition has been built upon the observations made by several pioneers during the nineteenth century and early part of 20th century.

Nutritional Classification of Foods

Since foods vary widely in their contents of various nutrients, they have been broadly grouped under three heads from the nutritional point of view: (i) Energy-yielding foods, (ii) Body building foods and (iii) Protective foods. These are briefly discussed below;

Energy-Yielding Foods

Foods rich in carbohydrates and fats are called energy-yielding foods. Cereals, roots and tubers, dried fruits, sugars and fats are included in this group. Cereals contain, in addition, fair amounts of proteins, minerals and certain vitamins and form the important sources of the above nutrients in poor dietaries.

Body -Building Foods

Oilseeds and nuts and low-fat oilseeds flours are included in the group of body-building foods.

Protective Foods

Foods rich in proteins, vitamins and minerals are termed protective foods. Milk, eggs, liver, green leafy vegetables and fruits are included in this group. Protective foods are broadly classified into two groups. (a) Foods rich in vitamins, minerals and proteins of high biological value, e.g., milk, eggs and liver, and (b) Foods rich in certain vitamins and minerals only, e.g., green leafy vegetables and fruits.

Objectives of the Study

- To estimate the effects of malnutrition in early childhood.
- To identify the health problem of children in Meelaneelithanallur block due to malnutrition.

Review of Literature

In India, there were distance sages of rise and fall in the status of children. A large volume of literature has been developed on malnutrition of children. Some of the literature relevant for this study is reviewed in this section.

Chowdhury (2015) A study on the features of the previous two national health policies of 1983 and 2002 and arrives at some recommendations for NHP 2015. Malnutrition is still widely prevalent in the country with 44% of the children under the age of five being underweight, while 72% of the infant and 52% of the women are anemia. More budgetary items permitting flexi-funding have been Introduced in the NRHM, (National rural health mission) and reproductive and child health budgets. However along with the primary healthcare component almost every other area of concern was included in the policy document like drinking water, sanitation, nutrition, environmental, impact etc. it would be a realistic assessment that in a decade with a modest amount of financial resources and some operational hand holding, we should be able to achieve USA in the country in respect of primary health care.

Methodology

The study is based on both Primary data and secondary data. Primary data is collected from the sample respondents through well structured interview schedule and Questionnaire. Secondary data is collected from text books, journals, magazines, News papers, Government Gazettes, internet

etc. Sample- nurse, Doctors, Anganwadi teachers, Anganwadi aayas midwife form PHC, were collected through personal visit to the home. For collection of primary data, interview schedule was used. A Preliminary interview schedule was constructed and administered to 300 households. The interview schedule was prepared keeping in view the objectives of the study. House wives' were also interviewed for more information. In addition to this, informal discussion was also held with heads of the families or other members of the families so as to cross check the information. The present study had been undertaken about health expenditure in Meelaneelithanallur block in Tirunelveli District. From the total population of 95104, the researcher has selected 300 respondents, as sample by using simple random sampling method. Sample- Nurse - 100, A nganwadi teachers - 100, Midwife from PHC-- 100,

Nutritional Profile of the Children

Breast milk is a rich source of hormones and growth factors like thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH), thyroxine, growth factor, prolactin, neurotensin, nerve growth factor(NGF), trophic factors and beta casomorphin. Human beta casomorphin is a CNS growth factor and it also mediates high concentration of hormones in breast milk than in maternal serum. NGF leads to dendritic arborisation. Enzymes like lysozyme, peroxidase and xanthine oxidase that promote cell maturation are found to be more in colostrums. Breast milk ensures better oxygen saturation and increases the bioavailability of trace elements like copper, magnesium, cobalt, selenium, iron, zinc etc, It contains less poisonous residues than cow's milk which are neurotoxic like chromium, aluminium, manganese ect. Infant foods and milk substitutes: Milk substitutes prepared from soybean has been used for many years in china and Indonesia for feeding infants. Recently, processes for the production of dried infant foods based on blends of soybean, groundnut protein and milk have developed in some countries. Feeding experiments with infants have shown that these foods promote good growth comparing well with milk foods. Groundnut protein has also been used for the preparation of toned vegetable milk. The following table illustrates the Patter of Pattern of intake of milk.

Table
Type of Milk wise Distribution of Sample respondents by Intake time

Types of Milk	Intake of Milk of the Respondents							Total
	time 1 to 2	2 to 3	3 to 4	4 to 5	5 to 6	6 to 7	7 to 8	
cow milk	34 (22.36)	60 (39.47)	11 (7.23)	15 (9.86)	8 (5.26)	14 (9.21)	10 (6.5)	152
Nestle Nan pro 1	6 (4)	44 (29.33)	31 (20.6)	11 (7.33)	8 (5.33)	33 (22)	17 (11.33)	150
Simile Advance	33 (17.5)	52 (27.6)	4 (2.12)	24 (12.7)	35 (18.6)	18 (9.5)	22 (11.7)	188
Farex	14 (6.5)	5 (2.32)	70 (32.5)	22 (10.23)	21 (9.7)	37 (17.20)	46 (21.39)	215
any other	14 (6.14)	10 (4.38)	35 (15.35)	15 (6.5)	35 (15.35)	40 (17.5)	79 (34.6)	228
Total	101 (10.8)	171 (18.32)	151 (16.18)	87 (9.32)	107 (11.46)	142 (15.7)	174 (18.6)	933 (100)

[Figures in the parentheses indicate the Percentage to respective totals]

Source: Computed from primary data

It is evident from table 4.5 that out of the 400 samples, 34 of the sample took cows milk 1 to 2 daily and, it is 22.33%. 60 babies observed consume cows milk 2to3 times daily, and it comes to 39.47% .11 of the sample took cow milk 3 to 4 times per day, and it is 7.23%.15 of the sample took cow milk 4 to 5 times daily, and it is 9.86%. 8 of the sample took cows milk 5 to 6 times per day, and it is 5.26%. 14 of the sample took cow milk 6 to 7 times daily, and it is 9.21%. 10 of the sample took cow’s milk 7 to 8 times per daily, and it is 6.5 %.

6 of the sample took Nestle Nan pro 1time 1 to 2, and it is 4%. 44 babies observed consume Nestle Nan pro 12to3 times daily, and it comes to 29.33%. 31 of the sample took Nestle Nan pro 13 to 4 times per day, and it is 20.6%. 11 of the sample took Nestle Nan pro 14 to 5 times daily, and it is 7.33%. 8 of the sample took Nestle Nan pro 15 to 6 times per day, and it is 5.33%. 33 of the sample took Nestle Nan pro 16 to 7 times daily, and it is 22%. 17 of the sample took Nestle Nan pro 17 to 8 times per daily, and it is 11.33 %.

33 of the sample took Simile Advance 1 to 2 daily, and it is 17.7%. 52 babies observed consume Simile Advance 2to3 times daily and it comes to 27.6%. 4 of the sample took Simile Advance 3 to 4 times per day, and it is 2.12%. 24 of the sample took Simile Advance 4 to 5 times daily, and it is 12.7%. 35 of the sample took Simile Advance 5 to 6 times per day, and it is 18.6%. 18 of the sample took Simile Advance 6 to 7 times daily, and it is 9.5%. 22 of the sample took Simile Advance 7 to 8 times per daily, and it is 11.7 %.

14 of the sample took Farex 1 to 2 daily, and it is 6.5%. 5 babies observed consume Farex 2to3 times daily, and it comes to 2.32% .70 of the sample took Farex 3 to 4 times per day, and it is 32.5%. 22 of the sample took Farex 4 to 5 times daily, and it is 10.23%. 21 of the sample took Farex 5 to 6 times per day, and it is 9.7%. 37 of the sample took Farex 6 to 7 times daily and it is 17.20 % .46 of the sample took Farex 7 to 8 times per daily, and it is 21.39 %.

14 of the sample took any other product 1 to 2 daily, and it is 6.14%. 10 babies observed consume any other product 2to3 times daily, and it comes to 4.38% .35 of the sample took any other product 3 to 4 times per day, and it is 15.35%. 15 of the sample took Any other product 4 to 5 times daily, and it is 6.5%. 36 of the sample took Any other product 5 to 6 times per day, and it is 15.35%. 40 of the sample took Any product 6 to 7 times daily, and it is 17.5%. 79 of the sample took any other Product 7 to 8 times per daily, and it is 34.

Type of milk wise Distribution of sample respondents by intake time is expressed in the following figure:

Figure Types of milk wise Distribution of sample respondents by intake time

Conclusions

The present study focused on the major sickness among the children in the study area. The main reason for the malnutrition, water proun diseases for children, the economic background of parents of malnutrition children etc and its helped to know the fact that the care from parents to their

children matter much, they should care their children with enough knowledge about their health condition there is a big role for the government to spend enough find in order to build a strong, healthy and empowered future to India.

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